

Customer Satisfaction on Reliability Dimension of Service Quality in Indian Higher Education

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Abstract : The present research studies analyses the students' satisfaction with university performance regarding the reliability dimension, ability of professors and staff to perform the promised services with quality to students in the post-graduate courses offered by Sri Venkateswara University in India. The research is done with the notion that the student compares the perceived performance with prior expectations. Customer satisfaction is seen as the outcome of this comparison. The sample respondents were administered with the schedule based on the stratified random technique for this study. Statistical techniques such as factor analysis, t-test and correlation analysis were used to accomplish the respective objectives of the study.

Keywords : satisfaction, reliability, service quality, customer

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